

Comparative Study of Morphological and Physico-Chemical Traits in Different Brassica Genotypes

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Abstract

Brassica species are members of the Brassicaceae family and several of them are commonly consumed by humans and oil industry. The present research was conducted for the comparative study of morphological and physico-chemical traits in different Brassica genotypes at experimental area of Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad during crop season 2022-2023. The experimental material was comprised of 11 genotypes of Brassica in a Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. The data was recorded on number of branches per plant, number of siliques per branch, number of siliques per plant, length of siliques (cm), height of the plant (cm), seed yield per plant, oil contents%, protein contents% and fatty acid profiling%. All the genotypes showed highly significant differences among them for all traits except for number of branches plant. Plant of the height, number of siliques per branch, number of siliques per plant, length of siliques and seed yield per plant showed highly significant and negative correlation with protein contents. Ecosenoic acid, erucic acid and glucosinolate had highly significant and positive correlation with protein content but oleic acid, linoleic acid, linolenic acid, palmitic acid and stearic acid showed highly significant and negative correlation with protein content. Oleic acid and stearic acid had significant and negative correlation with oil content. The results of the present study indicate that the oil contents of Shiralle was possibly suitable for human consumption and the oil contents of UAF 11, Dunkled and UAF 16 was suitable for industrial purposes. UAF 17 and Shiralle performed better for seed-related traits.

Keywords: Brassica genotypes, seed yield, oil contents, protein contents, fatty acids, correlation

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1. INTRODUCTION

Pakistan's economy is majorly engaged with agriculture since the independence and at that time it was considered the dominant sector of our economy. Brassica species (*Brassica napus*, *B. campestris*, *B. juncea* and *B. rapa*) belong to the Brassicaceae family (Abideen, 2013). Majority of the species are used as oilseed crops and some as pasture (Khan *et al.*, 2013). Mustard and rapeseed are abundant sources of oil, containing 44% to 46% high-quality oil. Additionally, each meal contains between 38 and 40 percent protein with a full complement of amino acids, including methionine, cystine and lysine (Abideen, 2013). Mustard and rapeseed are the main root of palatable oil after cotton seed, contributing significantly to the country's output of edible oil but their quality is quite poor due to the existence of significant amount of glucosinolates and erucic acid (Ahmad *et al.*, 2020). Canola, a cultivar of rapeseed developed by Canadian researchers, has low levels of glucosinolates and erucic acid (Sabagh *et al.*, 2019). During FY2022 (July-March), 2.754 million tonnes (MT) of edible oil/oil from oilseed for crushing total value Rs 662.657 billion (US\$ 3.681 billion) was imported. Local production of edible oil during this period is provisionally estimated at 0.460 MT. Total availability of edible oil during this period is estimated at 3.214 MT (Govt. of Pakistan, 2021-22).

Rapeseed (*B. napus*) is a notable crop used in the manufacture of vegetable oil, animal feed as well as biofuel on a global scale. Canola oil is often used in salad dressing, cooking as well as the creation of margarin. Additionally, lubricants and hydraulic fluids require canola oil (Cardoza and Stewart, 2003). In recent years, Brassica species have been linked to a broad spectrum of health benefits, involving anticancer characteristics, barriers against cardiovascular disease and aging, reproductive pathologies, cataracts etc. (Jahangir *et al.*, 2009; Akhlaghi and Bandy, 2010; Emmert *et al.*, 2010).

Brassica crops are cultivated in over 53 countries of the world and are considered as one of the oldest and earliest crop species domesticated by men (Kumar *et al.*, 2017). After soybean, Brassica oilseeds is the significant oilseeds crop in the world (Hasan *et al.*, 2006). Rapeseed was grown on 31 million ha of land worldwide in 2009 and its mean unit area production was roughly 20 thousand kg/ha (Farooq *et al.*, 2006). Canola is one of the key contributors of consumable oil in China and the Asian continent (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2007). Rapeseed-mustard (*Brassica spp.*), one of the seven consumable oil-seeds grown in India, accounts for 28.7% of the country's overall oil-seed production. It represents 27.9% of India's market for oil-seeds, making it the second-largest consumer oil-seed after groundnut. The global production of rapeseed-mustard and its oil is around 38-42 and 12-14 million tonnes (MT), accordingly (Shekhawat *et al.*, 2012).

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Pakistan is continuously deficient in the production of vegetable oil being an essential food commodity and its demand is fulfilled through import. Pakistan is an agrarian economy and producer of rapeseed and mustard but still not capable to produce sufficient amount of edible oil to meet the domestic needs. Size of the population and consumption/capita are the two main factors which determine the demand of sum total of edible oil for a nation (Afzal, 2009). The two main oil-producing crops in Pakistan are *B. campestris* L. and *B. napus* L. (Cruciferae). Rapeseed is a valuable crop for the oil industry. The production of rapeseed and mustard increased by 26.7 percent (Govt. of Pakistan, 2021-22).

Due to a rising imbalance between demand and supply, Pakistan is experiencing a significant shortage of edible oil. As a result, production cannot keep up with population growth (Fazal *et al.*, 2015). In order to meet the demand, a significant volume of foreign currency is spending each year for its importation (Hasan *et al.*, 2015). Different Brassica species' growth, development, yield and other physiological traits are influenced by abiotic stress (Jan *et al.*, 2017). Due to a lack of high-producing varieties, improper fertilizer application, cross-cultural operations, seed treatment, lack of timely availability and application of proper agriculture inputs, direct competition with major crops, cultivation of oilseed crops on marginal land, less attention toward the genetics of oilseed crop and lack of development of short duration varieties, production is relatively low (Kalita *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, it is essential to create better oilseed brassica varieties to bridge the gap between domestic production and imports of edible oil in the nation (Khatri *et al.*, 2005).

Objectives

Keeping in view the significance of Brassica, the experiment was conducted with the following objectives:

- ❖ To evaluate various morphological and physico-chemical traits in different Brassica genotypes.
- ❖ To recommend the best Brassica genotypes in high seed and oil yield for commercial cultivation and domestic cultivation.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted at experimental area of Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad during Crop season 2022-2023. The experimental material was comprised of 11 genotypes of Brassica in a Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. Fifteen plants were selected randomly from three rows per genotype to record data. The data was recorded on various traits. Analysis of variance (Steel *et al.*, 1997) was done by using Statistix 8.1 statistical

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software to find significant differences in Brassica genotypes. Means were compared by using Tukey HSD All-Pairwise Comparisons Test. Correlation analysis was employed, as suggested by Known and Torrie (1964), by using R 4.3.0 software to determine the strength of the association between yield and its associated attributes.

Plant material for research consisted of 11 Brassica genotypes presented here.

Table 1: Brassica Genotypes Used as Research Material

Sr. No.	Brassica genotypes
1	UAF11
2	UAF16
3	UAF12
4	UAF17
5	DGL
6	Shiralle
7	Punjab Sarsoon
8	Chakwal Sarsoon
9	Rainbow
10	Con1
11	Dunkled

Data Collection

Fifteen plants from each genotype were selected randomly from field and tagged. At plant maturity data were recorded on following traits for further evaluation and analysis:

Plant height (cm)

For morphological evaluation, height of the tagged plants was measured in centimeters from ground level to the top of the plant, with the help of a measuring tape at the time when plant reached the physiological maturity and average was calculated for further statistical analysis.

Length of silique (cm)

Silique length was recorded in centimeters on randomly selected pods per tagged plant by measuring the distance from the base to the tip of the individual pod and then their average was calculated.

No. of branches per plant

Total numbers of primary branches originating from the main stem were counted from the base and data was recorded on them. Average was calculated for further statistical analysis.

No. of silique per branch

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Total numbers of siliques per branch with maximum no. of siliques were counted on each tagged plants and average was calculated for further statistical analysis

No. of silique per plant

Total numbers of siliques present on each tagged plant were counted and data was recorded on them. Then average was calculated for further analysis.

Seed yield per plant (g)

Data on Seed yield plant⁻¹ was recorded in grams by threshing the all tagged plants and weighing grains from all selected plants by means of electrical balance. Average was calculated for further statistical analysis.

Oil content (%)

Oil contents (%) of representative samples of seeds were measure by Soxhlet Apparatus or Petroleum Ether Apparatus from fodder lab. After removal of impurities, the dried seeds were ground into fine powder using a grinder. The material that passed through an 80-mesh sieve was used for extraction purposes. The ground seeds (2g) were packed in filter paper and then fed into a Soxhlet extractor fitted with a 0.5-L round-bottom flask and a condenser. The extraction was continued for 2-3 h per sample using Petroleum Ether (40-60°C) heated by a water bath. After extraction, the Petroleum Ether was distilled off in a rotary evaporator. The oil extract was dried in petri dish till petroleum ether is completely evaporated, weighed and stored at 4 °C. Average was calculated for further statistical analysis. Following formula was used to measure oil percentage of each sample.

$$\text{Oil\%} = \text{Weight of Oil/weight of Sample} \times 100$$

Figure 1. Oil extraction during processing

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Figure 2. Extracted oil before petroleum ether evaporation

Figure 3. Extracted oil after petroleum ether evaporation

Protein and Fatty acids content (%)

Protein and fatty acids content (%) were measured from the lab of Oilseed Research Institute, Ayub Agriculture Research Institute, Faisalabad by NIR (Near Infrared Radiation). Average was calculated for further analysis. Thirty gram of seeds per sample was used for this purpose.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of Variance and Mean Comparisons

Table 2: Mean Squares Values from Analysis of Variance for Various Traits of Brassica Genotypes

Traits	Replications	Genotypes	Errors
Plant Height (cm)	522.77	2337.94**	167.55
No. of Branches per Plant	0.80576	0.64273 ^{NS}	0.69109
No. of Silique per Branch	267.3	31860.6**	347.1
No. of Silique per Plant	17885	1470480**	40738
Silique Length (cm)	0.10516	8.87764**	0.05074
Seed Yield per Plant (g)	102.33	4107.7**	112.26
Oil Content (%)	1.34226	9.38446**	1.06763
Protein Content (%)	0.15521	3.75221**	0.11278
Oleic Acid (%)	0.111	857.327**	0.766
Linoleic Acid (%)	0.4123	37.587**	0.234
Linolenic Acid (%)	0.01284	5.58426**	0.1983
Palmitic Acid (%)	0.30297	1.06605**	0.07397
Stearic Acid (%)	0.21429	1.00526**	0.11862
Ecosenoic Acid (%)	0.0935	16.4597**	0.0546
Erucic Acid (%)	0.18	1484.63**	0.13
Glucosinolates $\mu\text{mol/g}$	0.848	964.606**	23.815

*Significant ($P < 0.05$), **Highly Significant ($P < 0.01$) and Non-Significant ($P > 0.0$)

I. Plant Height (cm)

Means for plant height ranged from 99 to 186cm. Genotypes DGL showed maximum value for the plant height (186cm) while UAF11 showed minimum value for the plant height (99cm). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for plant height showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Khan and Khan (2003), Khan *et al.* (2006), Baradaran *et al.* (2007), Belete (2011), Afrin *et al.* (2011) and Abideen *et al.* (2013) also found same results for plant height.

II. No. of Branches per Plant

Means for no. of branches per plant ranged from 6.5 to 7.8. Genotypes Punjab Sarsoon showed the maximum value for no. of branches per plant (7.8) while UAF16 showed the minimum value for no. of branches per plant (6.5). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for no. of branches per plant showed that all the genotypes showed non-significant differences among them. Abideen *et al.* (2013) also found

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same result for no. branches per plant. Khan *et al.* (2006), Baradaran *et al.* (2007), Afrin *et al.* (2011) and Khan *et al.* (2013) reported significant differences among the genotypes for no. of branches per plant.

III. No. Silique per Branch (cm)

Means for no. of silique per branch ranged from 19-343. Genotypes UAF17 showed the maximum value for no. of silique per branch (343) while UAF11 showed the minimum value for no. of silique per branch (19). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for no. silique per branch (cm) showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Basalma (2008) Zebarjadi *et al.* (2011) and Zare (2011) also found same results for no. of silique per branch.

IV. No. Silique per Plant (cm)

Means for no. of silique per plant ranged from 143-2269. Genotypes UAF17 showed the maximum value for no. of silique per plant (2269) while UAF11 showed the minimum value for no. of silique per plant (143). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for no. silique per plant (cm) showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Khan *et al.* (2006), Baradaran *et al.* (2007), Afrin *et al.* (2011) and Khan *et al.* (2013) also found same results for no. of silique per plant. Abideen *et al.* (2013) reported non-significant differences among the genotypes for no. silique per plant.

V. Length of Silique (cm)

Means for silique length ranged from 3.1-7.73cm. Genotypes DGL showed maximum value for the silique length (7.73cm) while UAF11 showed minimum value for the silique length (3.1cm). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for length of silique (cm) showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Khan *et al.* (2006), Abideen *et al.* (2013) and Hassan *et al.* (2015) also found same results for silique length.

VI. Seed Yield per Plant (g)

Means for seed yield per plant ranged from 46-153g. Genotypes UAF17 showed the maximum value for seed yield per plant (153g) while UAF11 showed the minimum value seed yield per plant (46g). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for seed yield per plant showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Khan *et al.* (2006), (Baradaran *et al.* (2007), Belete (2011), Afrin *et al.* (2011) and Abideen *et al.* (2013) also found same results for seed yield per plant.

VII. Oil Content (%)

Means for oil content ranged from 43-48%. Genotypes UAF 11 showed the maximum value for oil content (48%) while Rainbow showed the minimum value for oil content (43%). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for oil contents showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Baradaran *et al.* (2007), Abideen *et al.* (2013), Sharafi *et al.* (2015), Ishaq *et al.* (2017) Rai *et al.* (2018) and Ahmad *et al.* (2022) also found same results for oil contents.

VIII. Protein Content (%)

Means for protein content ranged from 19-23%. Genotypes UAF 16 showed the maximum value for protein content (23%) while shiralle showed the minimum value for protein content (19%). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for protein contents showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Khan *et al.* (2006), Abideen *et al.*, (2013), Ishaq *et al.* (2017) and Ahmad *et al.* (2022) also found same results for protein content.

IX. Fatty Acids Contents

1) Oleic acid (%)

Means for oleic acid ranged from 7-67%. Genotypes Con 1 showed the maximum value for oleic acid (67%) while UAF 11 showed the minimum value for oleic acid (7%). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for oleic acid contents showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Sharafi *et al.* (2015), Ishaq *et al.* (2017), Rai *et al.* (2018) and Ahmad *et al.* (2022) also found same results for oleic acid.

2) Linoleic Acid (%)

Means for linoleic acid ranged from 7-19%. Genotypes Con 1 showed the maximum value for linoleic acid (19%) while UAF 11 showed the minimum value for linoleic acid (7%). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for linoleic acid showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Sharafi *et al.* (2015) and Rai *et al.* (2018) also found same results for Linoleic acid.

3) Linolenic Acid (%)

Means for linolenic acid ranged from 3.5-8%. Genotypes UAF 17 showed the maximum value for linolenic acid (8%) while UAF 16 showed the minimum value for linolenic acid (3.5%). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for linolenic acid contents showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Sharafi *et al.* (2015), Ishaq *et al.* (2017) and Rai *et al.* (2018) also found same results for linolenic acid.

4) Palmitic Acid (%)

Means for palmitic acid ranged from 3-5.2%. Genotypes Con 1 showed the maximum value for palmitic acid (5.2%) while UAF 11 showed the minimum value for palmitic acid (3%). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for palmitic acid contents showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Sharafi *et al.* (2015) and Rai *et al.* (2018) also found same results for Palmitic acid.

5) Stearic Acid (%)

Means for stearic acid ranged from 0.7-2.7%. Genotypes UAF 17 showed the maximum value for stearic acid (2.7%) while UAF 11 showed the minimum value for stearic acid (0.7%). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for stearic acid contents showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Sharafi *et al.* (2015) and Rai *et al.* (2018) also found same results for stearic acid.

6) Ecosenoic Acid (%)

Means for ecosenoic acid ranged from 0.03-8.1%. Genotype UAF 11 showed the maximum value for ecosenoic acid (8.1%) while Con 1 showed the minimum value for ecosenoic acid (0.03%). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for ecosenoic acid contents showed that all the genotypes showed highly significant differences among them. Sharafi *et al.* (2015) and Rai *et al.* (2018) also found same results for ecosenoic acid.

7) Erucic Acid (%)

Means for erucic acid ranged from 0.4-64%. Genotype UAF 11 showed the maximum value for erucic acid (64%) while Shiralle showed the minimum value for erucic acid (0.4%). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for erucic acid contents showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Sharafi *et al.* (2015), Ishaq *et al.* (2017), Rai *et al.* (2018) and Ahmad *et al.* (2022) also found same results for erucic acid.

8) Glucosinolates ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)

Means for glucosinolate ranged from 59-113 $\mu\text{mol/g}$. Genotype UAF 16 showed the maximum value for glucosinolate (113 $\mu\text{mol/g}$) while Dunkled showed the minimum value for glucosinolate (59 $\mu\text{mol/g}$). Analysis of variance of Brassica genotypes for glucosinolate contents showed that all the genotypes had highly significant differences among them. Ishaq *et al.* (2017) and Ahmad *et al.* (2022) also found same results for glucosinolate content.

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Mean values for plant height (cm)

Mean values for no. of branches per plant

Mean values for no. of silique per branch

Mean values for no. of silique per plant

Mean values for silique length (cm)

Mean values for seed yield per plant (g)

Mean values for oil contents (%)

Mean values for protein contents (%)

Mean values for oleic acid (%)

Mean values for linoleic acid (%)

Mean values for linolenic acid (%)

Mean values for palmitic acid (%)

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Mean values for linolenic acid (%)

Mean values for stearic acid (%)

Mean values for palmitic acid (%)

Mean values for ecosenoic acid (%)

Mean values for erucic acid (%)

Mean values for glucosinolate (µmol/g)

Figure 4. Mean Values for All Traits in Brassica Genotypes

Correlation Analysis

Analysis of correlation revealed that plant height, number of siliques per branch, number of siliques per plant, length of siliques and seed yield per plant showed highly significant and positive correlation among them. Khan *et al.* (2006) also found non-significant and negative correlation between no. of branches per plant and seed yield per plant. Khan and Khan (2003), Tusar *et al.* (2006), Rashid *et al.* (2015), Roy *et al.* (2015) and Hassan *et al.* (2015) observed the highest significant and positive correlations between seed yield per plant and no. of branches per plant. Oil contents had significant and positive correlation with plant height. Protein contents showed highly significant and negative correlation with plant height, number of siliques per branch, number of siliques per plant, length of silique and seed yield per plant but non-significant and negative correlation with number of branches per plant and oil contents. Abideen *et al.* (2013) and Azam *et al.* (2013) found non-significant and negative correlation between oil and protein contents. Oleic acid, linoleic acid, linolenic acid, palmitic acid and stearic acid had highly significant and negative correlation with oil and protein contents but ecosenoic acid and erucic acid showed highly significant and positive correlation with oil and protein contents. Sharafi *et al.*, (2015) observed a significant and positive correlation of oleic and stearic acids with oil contents. Glucosinolates had highly significant and positive correlation with protein contents but highly significant and negative correlation with oil contents. Ecosenoic acid, erucic acid and glucosinolates showed highly significant and negative correlation with oleic acid, linoleic acid, linolenic acid, palmitic acid and stearic acid. Sharafi *et al.* (2015) observed that erucic acid had highly significant and negative correlation with oleic acid, palmitic acid and stearic acid but highly significant positive correlation with linolenic acid.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis Among Morphological and Physico-Chemical Traits

	Ph	Nb	Sb	Sp	Ls	Sy	Oc	Pc	Oa	La	Lia	Pa	Sa	Eco	Eru	Gl
Ph	1	-0.21	**0.5	**0.54	**0.82	**0.5	*-0.37	** -0.7	**0.77	**0.63	**0.58	**0.63	**0.65	** -0.7	** -0.8	** -0.7
Nb		1	-0.12	-0.3	** -0.4	-0.27	-0.31	0.02	-0.11	0.08	0.02	0.11	0.02	0.25	0.07	**0.49
Sb			1	**0.96	**0.56	**0.93	0	** -0.8	**0.65	**0.66	**0.74	**0.48	**0.65	** -0.6	** -0.7	** -0.5
Sp				1	**0.63	**0.96	0.08	** -0.7	**0.66	**0.61	**0.72	**0.47	**0.61	** -0.6	** -0.7	** -0.6
Ls					1	**0.55	-0.23	** -0.7	**0.75	**0.56	**0.53	**0.53	**0.69	** -0.7	** -0.8	** -0.8
Sy						1	0.11	** -0.8	**0.59	**0.56	**0.71	**0.49	**0.55	** -0.7	** -0.6	** -0.6
Oc							1	0.11	** -0.5	** -0.45	** -0.2	** -0.4	** -0.47	**0.32	**0.41	** -0.1
Pc								1	** -0.7	** -0.72	** -0.8	** -0.8	** -0.67	**0.68	**0.77	**0.67
Oa									1	**0.94	**0.85	**0.8	**0.8	** -0.9	** -0.9	** -0.7
La										1	0.9	**0.8	**0.76	** -0.9	** -0.8	** -0.5
Lia											1	*0.76	**0.74	** -0.8	** -0.8	** -0.6
Pa												1	**0.69	** -0.7	** -0.7	** -0.5
Sa													1	** -0.7	** -0.8	** -0.5
Eco														1	**0.84	**0.69
Eru															1	0.65
Gl																1

*Represents significant differences at 5% level of confidence **represents highly significant differences at 1% level of confidence.

Ph= Height of the plant (cm), **Nb**= No. of Branches per plant, **Sb**= No. of Silique per branch, **Sp**= No. of Silique per plant, **Ls**= Length of Silique (cm), **Sy**= Seed yield per plant (g), **Oc**= oil contents %, **Pc**= Protein contents %, **Oa**= Oleic acid %, **La**= Linoleic acid %, **Lia**= Linolenic acid %, **Pa**= Palmitic acid %, **Sa**= Stearic acid %, **Eco**= Ecosenoic acid %, **Eua**= Erucic acid %, **Gl**= Glucosinolates µmol/g

4. CONCLUSION

Comparative study of 11 Brassica genotypes indicated that UAF 11, Shiralle, Dunkled and UAF 16 provides the highest oil contents. When compared to other fatty acids, UAF 11, Dunkled, and UAF 16 contained the highest amounts of erucic acid and glucosinolate contents, making them the best for commercial use. Shiralle, DGL, UAF 17, Rainbow and Con 1 had minimum amount of erucic acid and glucosinolate contents as compared to other fatty acids thus we can use these genotypes for domestic purposes by reducing the quantity of saturated fatty acids. UAF 16 is recommended for better protein contents. Also, UAF 17 and Shiralle were identified as superior genotypes for seed yield and hence were the best genetic resources to increase seed yield in Brassica.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abideen, S. N. U., F. Nadeem and S. A. Abideen. 2013. Genetic variability and correlation studies in *Brassica napus* L. genotypes. *Int. J. Innov. Appl. Sci.* 2:574-581.
- [2] Afrin, K. S., F. Mahmud, M. S. R. Bhuiyan and M. A. Rahim. 2011. Assessment of genetic varieties among advanced lines of *B. napus* L. *Agronomski Glasnik* 73:201-226.
- [3] Afzal, M. 2009. Population Growth and Economic Development in Pakistan. In the *Open Demogr. J.* 2:1-7.
- [4] Ahmad, H. B., S. Rauf, S. Saeed, I. Hussain and A. Khaliq. 2022. Genetic Exploration for quality aspects in *Brassica campestris*. *J. Agric. Res.* 60:81-87.
- [5] Ahmad, Z., E. A. Waraich, C. Barutcular, H. Alharby, A. Bamagoos, F. Kizilgeci, F. Ozturk, A. Hossain, Y. Bayoumi and A. E. Sabagah. 2020. Enhancing drought tolerance in *Camelina sativa* and *Canola napus* through application of selenium. *Pak. J. Bot.* 52:1927-1939.
- [6] Akhlaghi, M. and B. Bandy. 2010. Dietary broccoli sprouts protect against myocardial oxidative damage and cell death during ischemia-reperfusion. *Plant Foods Hum. Nutr.* 65:193-199.
- [7] Azam, S. M., Farhatullah, A. Nasim, S. Shah and S. Iqbal. 2013. Correlation studies for some agronomic and quality traits in *B. napus* L. *Sarhad J. Agric.* 29:548-550.
- [8] Baradaran, R., E. M. Heravan, F. Darvish and A. Mahdi. 2007. Study of correlation relationships and path coefficient analysis between yield and yield components in rapeseed (*B. napus* L.). *J. Agric. Sci.* 12:811-819.
- [9] Basalma, D. 2008. The correlation and path analysis of yield and yield components of different winter rapeseed (*B. napus* ssp. *oleifera* L.) cultivars. *Res. J. Agric. Biol. Sci.* 4:120-125.
- [10] Belete, Y. S. 2011. Genetic variability, correlation and path analysis studies in Ethiopian mustard (*B. carinata*) genotypes. *J. Plant Breed. Genet.* 5:328-338.
- [11] Cardoza, V. and C. N. Stewart. 2003. Increased Agrobacterium-mediated transformation and rooting efficiencies in canola (*B. napus* L.) from hypocotyl segment explants. *Plant Cell Rep.* 21:599-604.

- [12] Emmert, S. W., D. Desai, S. Amin and R. Jr. 2010. Enhanced Nrf2 dependent induction of glutathione in mouse embryonic fibroblasts by isoselenocyanate analog of sulforaphane. *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* 20:2675-2679.
- [13] Farooq, M., S. M. A. Basra, R. Tabassum and I. Afzal. 2006. Enhancing the performance of direct seeded fine rice by seed priming. *Plant Prod. Sci.* 9:446-456.
- [14] Government of Pakistan. 2021-22. Available online with updates at https://www.finance.gov.pk/survey_2022.html. Accessed on 13-05-2023
- [15] Hasan, E. U., T. Bibi, H. S. B. Mustafa, T. Mahmood, M. Tanveer, A. Kalyar and J. Saleem. 2015. Genetic evaluation and characterization for yield and related traits in mustard (*B. juncea* L.). *Res. J. Agri. Environ. Manag.* 4:82-87.
- [16] Hasan, M., F. Seyis, A. G. Badani, W. Friedt, W. Luhs and R. J. Snowdon. 2006. Analysis of genetic diversity in the *B. napus* L. gene pool using SSR markers. *Genet. Res. Crop Evol.* 53:793802.
- [17] Ishaq, M., R. Razi and S.A. Khan. 2017. Exploring genotypic variations for improved oil content and healthy fatty acids composition in rapeseed (*B. napus* L.). *J Sci. Food Agric.* 97:1924-1930.
- [18] Jahangir, M., H. K. Kim, Y. H. Choi and R. Verpoorte. 2009. Health-affecting compounds in Brassicaceae. *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Safety.* 8:31-43.
- [19] Jan, S. A., N. Bibi, Z. K. Shinwari, M. A. Rabbani, S. Ullah, A. Qadir and N. Khan. 2017. Impact of salt, drought, heat and frost stresses on morpho-biochemical and physiological properties of Brassica species: An updated review. *J. Rural. Dev. Agri.* 2:1-10.
- [20] Kalita, S. K., D. S. Chhonkar and M. Kanwat. 2019. Assessment of cluster front line demonstrations on rapeseed (*B. campestris* L.) in Tirap district of Arunachal Pradesh. *Indian J. Ext. Educ.* 55:17-22.
- [21] Khan, F. U., R. Udin, I. A. Khalil, I. H. Khalil and I. Ullah. 2013. Heritability and genetic potential of *Brassica napus* genotypes for yield and yield components. *J. Agric. Environ. Sci.* 13:802-806.
- [22] Khan, F.A., M. Younas and G. Mustafa. 2005. Correlation and factor wise contribution of the characters related to yield and quality of *B. juncea* L. *Int. J. Agric. Biol.* 7:257-259.
- [23] Khan, F.A., S. Ali, A. Shakeel, A. Saeed and G. Abbas. 2006. Correlation analysis of some quantitative characters in *B. napus* L. *J. Agric. Res.* 44:7-14.
- [24] Khan, R.S.A. and F. A. Khan. 2003. Evaluation of genetic potential of some Brassica germplasm collections. *J. Agric. Biol.* 5:630-631.
- [25] Khatri, A., I. A. Khan, M. A. Siddiqui, S. Raza and G. S. Nizamani. 2005. Evaluation of high yielding mutants of *B. juncea* cv. S-9 developed through gamma rays and EMS. *Pak. J. Bot.* 37:1-279.
- [26] Khayal, M., A. Rahnama and S. Lack. 2016. Assessment, correlation, step wise regression and path coefficient analysis of yield associated traits in rapeseed (*B. napus* L.) cultivars for achieve genetic improvement. *Adv. Environ. Boil.* 23:305-312.
- [27] Kumar, S., P. Chand, A. Sirohi, V. Kumar and P. Kumar. 2009. Studies on relationship among yield components and selection criteria for yield improvement in Indian mustard (*B. juncea* L. Czern & Coss.). *Progressive Agriculture*, 13:181-186.

- [28] Kumar, V., K. R. Krishna and K. Jangid. 2017. Estimation of Combining Ability for the Yield, Yield Attributing Traits and Oil Content in Indian mustard (*B. juncea* L. Czern & Coss). *Trend. Biosci.* 10:8409-8414.
- [29] Rai, G.K., S. Bagati, P.K. Rai, S.K. Rai and M. Singh. 2018. Fatty Acid Profiling in Rapeseed Mustard. *Int. J. Curr. Microbial. App. Sci.* 7:148-157.
- [30] Ramachandran, S., S. K. Singh, C. Larroche, C. R. Soccol and A. Pandey. 2007. Oil cakes and their biotechnological applications. *Bioresource Technol.* 98:2000-2009.
- [31] Rashid, M. H. U., S. Parveen and M. S. R. Bhuiyan. 2015. Morphological attributes species identification of oleiferous Brassica species and better parent selection criteria for *B. juncea*. *Int. J. Res.* 7:19847-19854.
- [32] Sabagh. E. A., A. Hassan, Z. Ahmad and H. Saneoka. 2019. Effects of drought stress on the quality of major oilseed crops: Implications and possible mitigation strategies. *Appl. Ecol. Environ. Res.* 17:4019-4043.
- [33] Sharafi, Y., M.M. Majidi, S.A.H. Goli and F. Rashidi. 2015. Oil Content and Fatty Acids Composition in Brassica Species. *Int. J. Food Proper.* 18:2145-2154.
- [34] Shekhawat, K., S. S. Rathore, O. P. Premi, B. K. Kandpal and J. S. Chauhan. 2012. Advances in agronomic management of Indian mustard (*B. juncea* L.) Czernj. Cosson). *Int. J. Agron.* 10:14-19.
- [35] Steel, R.G.D., J. H. Torrie and D.A. Dickey. 1997. Principles and procedures of statistics: A biometrical approach (3rded.) McGraw-Hill New York.
- [36] Tusar, P., S. Maiti and B. Mitra. 2006. Variability, correlation and path analysis of the yield attributing characters of mustard. *Res. Crops.* 7:191-193.
- [37] Zabarjadi, A., M. Kakaei and A. Mostafaie. 2011. Genetic variability of some traits in rapeseed (*B. napus* L.) under drought and non-stress conditions. *Biharean Biologist* 5:127-131.
- [38] Zare, M. 2011. Interrelationship between seed yield and related traits in rapeseed (*B. napus* L.). *J. Agric. Res.* 6:6684-6689.